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ORIGINAL ARTICLE

An alternative Technique for Transaortic Celiac Plexus block

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Abstract

Introduction: Celiac plexus block is one of the most effective treatments for relief of intractable upper abdominal due to upper abdominal malignancy or chronic pancreatitis. The efficacy of celiac plexus block to relieve pain varies in different techniques; transaortic approach being safer with higher success rate. It has been tried with Classical approach only. We have tried to introduce a safer and easier technique of transaortic celiac plexus block and have compared it with classical approach.

Method: In modified method we have rotated C-arm obliquely towards left side till transverse process of L1 vertebra is merged with vertebral body and then cranially to bring 12th rib touching upper part of L1. A triangle is thus formed bounded by lateral aspect of L1 vertebral body, inferior border of 12th rib and an imaginary line drawn laterally from lower border of L1. Needle is placed at the center of the triangle and introduced in tunnel view. Once we cross aorta as assessed by feelings of puncturing aorta twice, C-arm is checked by lateral view. Needle placement is checked by dye.

Results: Comparing the two group needles were placed transaortic in 55% cases in classical approach requiring 3.05 attempts on average as compared to modified approach where needle placement were transaortic in 92% cases requiring 1.79 attempts on average. Needle was placed by 1st attempt in 54.17% cases and required 10.9167 minute time to complete the procedure in modified approach compared to classical approach where needle placement by 1st attempt was in 15% cases requiring

31.05 minutes average time to complete the procedure. All these data are statistically significant.

Discussion: With all advantage of performing procedure in tunnel view the modified approach requires less time, less number of attempts and more chance of placing the needle through aorta. Chances of 2nd needle placement is less requiring less volume of drug, less procedure time and safer. ■

Key Words

Celiac plexus block; Transaortic approach; Upper abdominal malignancy; Chronic pancreatitis; Pain management.

Introduction

Celiac plexus block is one of the most effective treatments for relief of intractable upper abdominal and mid-back pain due to upper abdominal malignancy or chronic pancreatitis. The percutaneous celiac plexus block technique was first described by Kappis in 1914. He subsequently performed a series of 200 cases in 1918. Several other authors modified the technique^{2,3,4} but Kappis's classic posterior approach to the celiac plexus continues to serve the basis for contemporary techniques¹. CT and Ultrasonography guided techniques are also gaining popularity nowadays.

The efficacy of celiac plexus block to relieve pain varies in different techniques and it also varies according to the pain generator pathology eg, in pancreatic cancer and other upper abdominal malignancies⁵⁻⁶. Furthermore, complications such as paraplegia, pneumothorax, and liver or kidney puncture have also been reported at times with

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conventional techniques^{7,8,9}. Transaortic approach has been described as safer with higher success rate in literatures^{10,11}. Transaortic technique has not been described in details. As per description in literature we should enter skin 1 to 1.5cm more medial and follow the classical approach on the left side. If aorta is coming on the needle trajectory, then it is called transaortic approach. Difficulties in this approach are:

1. Success rate of going through aorta is not very high.
2. Higher number of attempts are required to reposition the needle and going through aorta.
3. Time taken to go through aorta is higher.

We have described a simpler technique where chance of going through aorta is higher with lesser number of attempts. With modified technique we performed 24 cases, only in two cases the needle placements were not transaortic.

Materials and Methods

After institutional review board permission 44 patients were selected for celiac plexus block in two years time period. Informed consents were taken in all cases. Two of them were suffering from benign chronic pancreatitis, rest all other were suffering from upper abdominal malignancies.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Intractable upper abdominal pain due to upper abdominal malignancy or chronic pancreatitis.
2. Patient may have radiating pain towards mid-back or right shoulder.
3. Patients of either sex or any age group were taken.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Huge ascites (patient cannot lie prone)
2. Debilitation and low blood pressure (systolic below 80mm of Hg).
3. Distant metastasis with pain in other areas also.
4. Coagulopathies.
5. Patient refusal.

Patients were randomly allocated into two groups. In group 1 classical approach was tried. In group 2 our modified technique was tried.

In both groups patients were taken at the operating room and intravenous catheter and fluid were in place. Systemic antibiotic was given and procedure was done under fluoroscopic guidance. Patients were kept admitted for one day. In both groups number of attempts to reach the target as

confirmed by dye was noted. (Redirection below subcutaneous tissue is not counted as another attempt. When the needle is taken outside skin or at subcutaneous tissue and inserted again was considered as another attempt.) The time for needle placements in two groups were noted. The time was calculated after draping and from the beginning of adjustment of C-arm. It was noted up to the completion of procedure (It includes bilateral needle placement also when required). Whether the procedure was transaortic or not was also noted. The two groups were compared according to these four parameters.

1. Whether needle was placed by first attempt.
2. Whether needle is placed transaortic.
3. Total number of attempts required.
4. Time required completing the procedure.

In group 1 the procedure was performed as described in text books. Needle entry point is marked 5-7.5 cm away from midline on left side, where lateral border of paraspinal muscles are intersecting 12th rib. Needle is directed in front of lower half of L1 vertebral body. Needle placement is confirmed by AP and lateral view. If aorta is coming on the way as felt like passing the needle through a rubber band and confirmed by aspiration of blood and pulsating dye in front of aorta, then needle is placed transaortic. If needle puncture is not transaortic, another needle is placed on the right side. Time taken to place the left sided needle and number of attempts to place it are noted and compared. In 16 patients celiac plexus block was done by the classical technique.

Modified technique :

In group 2 the procedure was performed by our modified

Fig 1: Needle entry point more medial and slightly superior than classical

technique. Patient was lying prone and C-arm was first placed AP.

Fig. 1 shows Needle entry point more medial and slightly superior than classical approach, 12th rib and L1 vertebral body were identified. C-arm is then rotated obliquely on the left side till transverse process of L1 vertebra merges

Fig 2: C-arm is Rotated obliquely till transverse process is merged with vertebral body and cranially till 12th rib touches upper part of L1 vertebral body

Fig 3: C-arm in different positions

with antero-lateral margin of L1. C-arm is then tilted cranially so that 12th rib comes to touch lateral side of the L1 vertebral body in its upper part.

Thus a triangle is formed medially by antero-lateral border of L1 vertebral body, laterally by lower border of 12th rib and base is formed by an imaginary

Fig 4: Triangle formed by the vertebral body, 12th rib and imaginary line

Fig 5: Needle in tunnel view

line drawn laterally from the lower border of L1 vertebral body. The needle entry point will be at the center of this triangle.

22G 15cm long needle is introduced in tunnel vision and seen as a point. It is introduced till aorta is encountered.

Fig 6: Lateral view showing needle in front of vertebral body of L1

Fig 7: Dye in front and around the aorta

Stylet of the needle was removed and aspiration of blood was noticed. Lateral view was taken to confirm the correct depth of the needle.

Dye was then injected under cine vision. Dye was seen to run away distally. Needle was then further introduced and same type of feelings noted when anterior wall of aorta was punctured. No blood was seen after removing stylet. Dye was injected again and it was seen to pulsate along aortic pulsation in lateral view. (Fig. 7)

Final needle tip positioning was confirmed by AP and lateral view. If aorta was not punctured, a second needle was placed from the right side. 15cc of 60% alcohol was injected through the left sided needle when it was transaortic. Another 15cc was injected through second needle on the right side if it was not transaortic.

Advantages of modified techniques are:

1. As it is done under tunnel view, it is easier and faster to perform the procedure.
2. As chance of hitting L1 vertebra is less, it is less painful also.
3. Chance of passing through aorta is much higher.

Results

Total of the 44 patients were enrolled in the study. Twenty patients went for block by classic approach. Whereas 24

Fig 8: Celiac plexus block by classic and modified approach

Fig 9: Needle placement a first attempt in celiac plexus block by classic and modified approach

Fig 10: Needle placement a first attempt for celiac plexus block by modified approach

patients went for modified approach. Comparing the two group's needle was placed at first attempt in 15 % cases in Classic Approach Group but 45.83 % cases in Modified

Fig 11: % of transaortic needle placement classic approach

Fig 12: % of transaortic needle placement modified approach

Approach Group. (Fig. 8)

Transaortic needle placement was achieved in 55 % cases in classic approach where as 91.667 % needle placement was achieved in modified approach (Fig. 11 & 12) . The maximum number of attempt being 5 and minimum being 1 for celiac plexus block by the two methods combined was elucidated. Mean number of attempts for performing celiac plexus block by two methods combined (Fig. 13) was 2.3636 with a standard deviation of 1.29563 was found. Maximum time taken was 36 min and the minimum time 4 min for these procedures with two approaches combined was elucidated. The mean time taken for the

Fig 13: Histogram for number of attempts by all two methods combined (classic + modified)

Fig 14: Histogram for time taken by all two methods combined (classic+modified)

Fig 15: Number of attempts by classic approach

procedure was 20.0682 with a standard deviation of 25 was found. (Fig. 14)

For classic approach a maximum of 5 attempts and minimum of 1 attempt was needed. The calculated mean for number of attempt in classic approach is 3.0500 with a standard deviation of 1.23438 and a variance of 1.524 was found. (Fig. 15)

With a minimum attempt of one and a maximum of four for modified approach was elucidated. The mean number of attempt for modified approach is 1.7917 with a

standard deviation of 1.06237 and a variance of 1.129 was found. (Fig.16)

In classic approach minimum time of 25 min and maximum ranging up to 36 min was elucidated. The mean time for classic approach is 31.0500 min with a standard deviation of 2.96426 min and a variance of 8.787 was found. (Fig. 17)

Maximum time taken being 27 min with a minimum time of 4 minutes for celiac block by modified technique was elucidated. The mean time for modified approach is 10.9167 min with a standard deviation of 6.58 and a variance of 43.297 was found. (Fig. 18)

The distribution of a quantitative variable (e.g., procedure

Fig 16: Number of attempts by modified approach

Fig 17: Time of intervention by classic approach

Fig 18: Time of intervention by modified approach

time, and number of attempts) was compared by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov nonparametric two-sample test. The number of attempts is significantly less in the modified technique with a p value of .010

Discussion

The major disadvantage of fluoroscopy guided procedure is that fluoroscopic images are 2-dimensional. We need to build 3 dimensional images from these 2-dimensional images while placing the needle and need to confirm by repeated Antero-Posterior and lateral view. In that process we need to redirect the needle several times to reach the target.

One important way to overcome this drawback is to perform the procedures in tunnel vision. When the needle is placed in tunnel vision it is seen as a point and if direction of needle is maintained properly we can reach the target without redirecting the needle. In case of transaortic celiac plexus block we do the procedure on left side where aorta comes on the way, which tells us the depth as well. But the depth should be checked by lateral view.

Conclusion

It has been documented that transaortic approach is safer as lesser amount of alcohol is required to perform the block. It is also more effective as we are injecting the drug right at target, where density of the celiac plexus is maximum, which is around the aorta.

Further evaluation is required to proof superiority of this modified technique over classical approach to perform

transaortic celiac plexus block.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors confirm that there are no conflicts of interest related to this original article.

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